

Study of Constructed Wetland Method for Waste Water Treatment

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Abstract: -

Constructed wetlands (CWs) are predominantly controlled by microbes and their metabolic processes. Microorganisms are crucial in converting complex carbon-based compounds into simpler organic compounds, like nitrate, phosphate, phosphorus, and amino acids. The research concludes that microorganisms can efficiently eliminate harmful biological substances using anaerobic or aerobic breakdown processes while treating wastewater. The main processes for achieving this are aeration and fermentation, which convert biological pollutants into nontoxic byproducts like water, CO₂, and NO₂. Furthermore, the constructed wetland method involves important activities including nutrient recycling in the wastewater at the root zone of plants, a process referred to as phytoremediation. Additionally, it encompasses the filtration of solids and gravels at various levels and the aerobic and anaerobic transformation of organic and inorganic compounds, which will be affected by the soil's physical and chemical elements and environmental conditions.

Keywords: - Wastewater, CW, Hybrid, Treatment Method, Adsorption, Wetlands, Wetland Reactor.

Introduction: -

At the initial research level, "The current technique for purifying raw water is not producing efficient results, so it cannot be said that the water treated in the construction wetland is drinkable. As a research scholar in India, we have chosen to study this technique to sanitize wastewater. After conducting several case studies using newspapers and research papers, we have found that the existing technique for treating wastewater is not effective for treating wastewater."

As we started the investigation of the constructed wetland, after executing the initial attempts, we realized that this conventional method and material takes a lot of time to purify water. Hence for the reduction of time of treatment in the conventional wetland filter material, we replaced a few materials and came up with two different efficient materials i) Activated

charcoal ii) Recron fiber (synthetic cotton). After testing this material in a laboratory in a different mould, we reached to the conclusion that these two materials can remove almost 85 to 90% of solids present in water and wastewater. While executing this experiment, we tested different raw water and wastewater samples and we got the desired results with these materials during testing. We utilized the college laboratory to test basic parameters like pH and turbidity and the remaining parameters were tested in the authorized laboratory of the irrigation department, the activated charcoal of 800ID which is of very high-quality adsorbing material and recron fibers (Synthetic polyester fibers) of 45 microns and 50-micron size is highly recommended for the removal of suspended and dissolved solids from wastewater.

Proposed reactor contains five layers of material excluding plants. Plants also play a very important role in treating the raw water because the root of the plant can remove nitrate, VOCs and toxic waste from the wastewater and this process is called phytoremediation. The first three layers of the reactor have natural materials like soil, sand, and pebbles. But in the new age constructed wetlands need more efficiency hence used advanced techniques and some advanced materials which helped us to gain higher efficiency for that we tested different materials suitable for the efficient removal of contaminants and after detailed research, finalised activated charcoal and recron fiber as material for the fourth and fifth layer.

The following are major impurities removed in the CW reactor:

➤ Suspended Solids Removal

The main impurity found in wastewater is suspended solids (SS). While removing SS from wastewater can be a laborious task, CW reactors offer an efficient solution thanks to their multiple filter layers, which aid in the processes of sedimentation, flocculation, and filtration. Vander Waal's force of attraction is also used to eliminate charged particles, such as colloidal particles. Complex organic molecules and harmful metals can be eliminated using CW reactor.

➤ Nitrogen Removal:

Fresh wastewater has significant quantities of nitrogenous chemicals and nitrogen gas, particularly in household wastewater. If this wastewater enters a freshwater body, it may promote eutrophication in the body that receives it. The important processes surrounding the root zone in CWs are adsorption, oxidation, vegetation absorption & uptake, ammonification, and the nitrification-denitrification complex, these mechanisms enable wetlands to remove nitrogen from wastewater. Within CWs, a perennial marsh plant transforms inorganic

nitrogen forms into organic chemicals that are advantageous to microorganisms' cells and tissues.

The main process for removing nitrogen from wastewater in wetlands is often understood to be the nitrification-denitrification complex, which is aided by microorganisms.

➤ BOD and COD Removal

Through the action of adsorption within the void area, the surfaces of gravel and rock media operate to trap organic materials. Microorganisms then target the trapped organic substances and begin to consume them. For bacteria, organic matter—which is almost entirely composed of carbon—provides energy. This process is aided by wetlands plants, which provide oxygen to the root zone, allowing organic carbon compounds converted to CO₂. In addition, different separation techniques, such as adsorption and absorption, can be used to remove soluble organic materials. The decomposition of organic matter in wetlands is caused by important processes that involve biochemical changes. These mechanisms can result in the formation of organic material through biomass amalgamation as well as the removal of some organic elements through gasification or mineralization.

➤ Metal Removal

A Constructed wetland reactor uses several procedures to treat industrial wastewater and remove metals.

To eliminate metals in our constructed wetland reactor.

We have added a layer of designed thickness of sand and gravel to the reactor to aid in the vital process of filtering, which is the elimination of metal. High-specific gravity metals in the form of suspended solids, like cadmium, lead, silver, and zinc, have efficiently removed this layer from wastewater.

Physical processes such as sedimentation and precipitation take place following other mechanisms that combine heavy metals into particles that can sink. In artificial wetlands, heavy metals may bind to the soil or sediment, or they may chelate or combine with other substances.

Objectives of Project

1 Assessing Treatment Efficiency:

- Contaminants Reduction: Measure the reduction in the amount of pollutants such as SS, nitrate and nitrogenous compounds, pH, BOD and COD present in the wastewater.
- Water Quality Improvement: Assess the improvement in water quality parameters such as SS, nitrate and nitrogenous compounds, pH, BOD and COD.

2. Evaluating Hydraulic Performance:

- Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT): Govern the optimum HRT for maximum treatment efficiency.
- Flow Variation and Patterns: Examine the flow patterns and variation within the retention time in the wetland reactor to identify precise handling time with outlet discharge.

Literature Review

In [1] Researchers focused on Plant components such as *Vetiveria zizanoides*, *Citrus Limon*, *Arachis hypogaea*, and *Indian Phyllanthus emblica* are being studied as potential approaches to reduce suspended solids from hard drinking water. The sample was collected from a tubewell on the peripheries of Chennai and tested using a TDS meter to determine the TDS level, which was around 1,400 parts per million. Each vertical glass column carrying the chosen plant materials was packed individually. fifty millilitres of hard water were put into the column at a discharge of 10ml/min to commence the process. The reduction in the dissolved solids concentration in the specimens was assessed. The proportion of the decrease of Suspended solids from collected water samples was calculated for both the initial and final loadings. It is clear that *Vetiveria zizanoides* has the highest TDS decrease (61%), followed by *Citrus Limon* (46%), *Arachis hypogaea* (52%), and peanut husk (52%).

In [2], As per Researchers Water pollution recently become a major environmental issue. The Pavana, Mula, and Mutha rivers, which run into the city of Pune and the industrial zone, are contaminated with partly unprocessed industrial waste from Nallas and untreated home sewage. Waste generation, industrial expansion, and population increase have all contributed to continuous issues for the city. Some essential water quality indicators, such as dissolved

oxygen, biological oxygen requirement, and phosphate levels, have all fallen in the river. According to statistics from the Maharashtra Pollution Control Board, all pollution metrics in the Pimpri and Chinchwad rivers exceed permissible levels. Freshwater resources are essential for maintaining the optimal habitat for all living forms, including people and abiotic components, as well as ground and surface waters. Surface water covers about 3% of the land of Pimpri Chinchwad. Household sewage generated by inhabitants' daily activities is handled in many Municipal Corporation treatment plants before being discharged into waterways in compliance with sewage quality standards. The SCADA System manages ten independent sewage treatment units that operate around the city. However, due to rising population and pollution, smaller-scale remedies must be implemented to halt sewage water production at its source.

In [3], Eureau is an acronym for the European Federation of National Associations for Water and Wastewater Facilities. It deals with drinking water and undertook an assessment of raw drinking water sources and drinking water treatment methods used in Europe. subsurface water, surface water, spring water with synthetic recharge, and banks of rivers filtration were the sources of untouched water. Alternatives for treatment encompass having no treatment at all, technologically advanced treatment, standard methods, and a mix of advanced and standard methods. The response addressed the utilities cooperative in Eureau, which provides drinking water to 45% of the population. Surface water and groundwater are the primary sources of raw water (more than 85%). 39% of the total drinking water supply consists of either untreated drinking water., On the other side, 13% of drinking water is unsanitary. The existence of new compounds in raw water sources, a lack of disinfection, and the potential creation of disinfection byproducts all offer problems to the European drinking water business. To tackle these problems, more research is needed. This includes creating quantitative relationships between structure and activity to predict and comprehend the rates at which emerging contaminants are removed from treatment technologies, implementing Water Safety Plans in operation to safeguard the healthfulness of drinking water and strengthening disinfection methods and practices.

In [4], This research article used a reactor with a photoactive refill to extract phenol from water. Following thermal stabilization, the titanium dioxide was immobilized as a thin film on the base material. The Titania coating was put over the glass cloth. According to research findings, Titania coatings have a high level of photocatalytic function for breaking down

phenol in water. Phenol entirely disappeared in 23 hours, which is a rather short time. After multiple stages of water treatment, the produced coatings exhibit exceptional stability. When the activity of the photocatalyst decreases, it becomes necessary to replace the reactor or certain parts of it. This problem is resolved by the suggested reactor with a photoactive refill. The only readily replaceable part in the event of a photocatalyst activity decline is the photoactive refill.

3.1 Designing Steps and Implementation

Constructing and implementing a wastewater treatment reactor involves several critical steps to ensure effective treatment and environmental responsibility.

The following steps are finalised for Designing Constructed Wetlands Reactor and treatment process as follows: -

- **Source Identification:** The first action in the process is to detect the sources of wastewater that will be subject to treatment. This crucial step helps pinpoint sampling locations and tailor the treatment approach to the specific wastewater composition.
- **Surface Loading Rate:** Determining the appropriate surface loading rate is essential for efficient treatment. Initial trials and testing guide the finalization of this rate, ensuring that the reactor receives wastewater at a sustainable and effective level.
- **Filtration Material Testing:** The selection of suitable filtration materials is vital to the success of the constructed wetland. To make the right choice, moulds are prepared for testing various filtration materials, evaluating their effectiveness in wastewater treatment.
- **CW Reactor Design:** The functionality of a constructed wetland reactor is largely dependent on its specified dimensions and design. Creating a fixed and well-thought-out structure ensures that the reactor efficiently treats incoming wastewater.
- **Wetland Construction:** The actual construction of the wetland structure involves the combination of specific layers, including gravel, sand, and charcoal material. These layers work together to filter and cleanse the wastewater effectively.
- **Aquatic Plant Introduction:** To enhance biological activities within the constructed wetland, aquatic plants are installed. These plants contribute to the treatment efficiency by promoting biological interactions that aid in water purification.

- **Water Parameter Analysis:** Monitoring key water characteristics such as dissolved oxygen (DO), total solids (TS), BOD, COD, Nitrate and phosphate levels is vital. This analysis provides insights into the effectiveness of the effluent treatment process, ensuring that treated water meets the required quality standards.
- **Efficiency Assessment:** By analysing samples from the wetland system, the effectiveness of the constructed wetland in treating wastewater is evaluated. This assessment helps to perfect the system and make necessary adjustments for optimal performance.
- **Water Utilization:** Finally, the treated water from this method is versatile and can be applied for various purposes, including gardening, flushing, construction, and decorative applications. This sustainable approach to water treatment allows for responsible and efficient water use.

Result: -

Trail-1

summer Season

Tabular form

Sr. No.	Parameters	Before	After	Permissible Limit
1	pH	7.2	7.6	6.6-8.5
2	BOD	68	6.4	less than 5 mg/l
3	Nitrate	5.76	2.10	1 mg/l

Table 1: Testing Results of Sample 1 in trial I

Graphical Form

Graph 01. Combine results of sample 1 in trial-I

The Testing were done on the various parameters such as pH, BOD, NITRATE, etc. In this testing report we have found that the given parameters are satisfied and under the permissible limit. The removal efficiency of CW reactor is high, nearly 80-85% removal efficiency obtained from CW reactor. The biological, Chemical and physical parameters none satisfied in this CW reactor.

Individual Graphs: -

Graph 02. Individual Results of sample1 in trial-II

pH :- The pH of water of drinkable water is 6.5-8.5 in this permissible limit. In this test the pH of water sample is under the acceptable limit,

Graph 03. Individual Results of sample1 in trial-III

BOD :- The BOD (Biological oxygen demand). Permissible limit of BOD is less than 5mg/l, in this test we have reduce the BOD in large amount.

Graph 04. Individual Results of sample1 in trial-IV

Nitrate :-

The nitrate permissible limit is 1mg/l, in this test we have reduce the nitrate amount from the wastewater by the help of CW reactor.

Conclusion: -

In Conclusion, the study decisively validates that constructed wetlands employing phytoremediation represent a practical, supportable and ecological solution for treating domestic wastewater. They present a tangible means to address the escalating requirement for effective wastewater management while concurrently advocating for environmental preservation and sustainability.

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